

Studies on the synthesis of ammonium salts of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) to enhance its bioregulating potential

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Abstract : Tertiary amines viz. 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (6a), 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(2-chlorophenoxy)acetate (6b), (3-*N,N*-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(2-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oate (11a) and (3-*N,N*-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-enoate (11b) were prepared through the formation of glycidyl ester. Primary amine (ethanolamine), secondary amines (diethylamine and piperidine) and the synthesized tertiary amines (6a, 6b, 11a and 11b) were reacted with 2,4-dichloroacetic acid (2,4-D) to get secondary (1a), tertiary (1b and 1c) and quaternary (1d-g) ammonium salts. These salts (1a-g) were tested on rice (*Oryza sativa*, PR-114) for their biological activity. All the tested compounds are found to possess more plant growth retardant activity than that of 2,4-D.

Keywords : Ammonium salts, 2,4-D, plant growth retardants, *Oryza sativa*.

Introduction

Ammonium salts are reported to influence the growth and development of plants. Plant growth regulators (PGRs) are the organic compounds, other than nutrients, which, in very small concentrations applied as a spray to foliage or as a liquid drench to soil around a plant's base, produce major growth changes, promote, inhibit, or otherwise modify any physiological process in a plant². They are used to control the shoot growth of containerized herbaceous and ornamental crops^{3,4}. Today, herbicides and plant growth regulators, together with improved management procedures, can be used to eliminate vegetation in areas such as industrial sites and storage yards; to control weeds along highways and railroads; to eliminate weeds in ornamental plantings, turf, and aquatic sites; and to slow the growth of turf grasses and other vegetation. Phenoxy herbicides are referred as auxin-like herbicides. They are solids in their acid form. As such they are of little use, as their solubility is low and they do not readily penetrate plant leaves⁵. So, the phenoxy compounds are modified and their amine salts can be used as growth regulators. Plant growth retardants are applied in agronomic and horticultural crops to reduce unwanted longitudinal shoot growth without lowering plant pro-

ductivity. In continuation to our work on the synthesis and growth retarding activity of trialkyl ammonium compounds^{6,7}, we have now synthesized seven new ammonium salts of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid and tested them as plant bioregulator on growth of *Oryza sativa* (PR-114).

Results and discussion

2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (1) used for the preparation of ammonium salts was prepared by reacting 2,4-dichlorophenol with chloroacetic acid in the presence of NaOH. The acid (1) was obtained by acidification with hydrochloric acid from the corresponding salt. The m.p. of the acid was comparable with that reported in the literature. Tertiary amines : 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (6a) and 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(2-chlorophenoxy)acetate (6b) were prepared by reacting the *p*-chlorophenoxyacetic acid (3a) and *o*-chlorophenoxyacetic acid (3b) (prepared from *p*-chlorophenol (2a) and *o*-chlorophenol (2b), respectively by their reaction with chloroacetic acid in the presence of aq. NaOH), separately with excess of epichlorohydrin⁸ in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate⁹ to get the mixture of oxiran-2-ylmethyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (4a) and 3-

chloro-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (**5a**); oxiran-2-ylmethyl-2-(2-chlorophenoxy)acetate (**4b**) and 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(2-chlorophenoxy)acetate (**5b**) respectively, as evidenced by its TLC^{10,11} (2 spots). Out of these two products, one product (**4a/4b**) was formed in which nucleophilic attack of carbonyl oxygen was on carbon carrying chlorine and another (**5a/5b**) formed in which

this attack occurs on carbon carrying epoxy oxygen. The mixture was separately reacted with secondary amine (diethylamine¹²) in the presence of absolute alcohol¹³ to get the respective hydroxyl tertiary amines, 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (**6a**) and 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(2-chlorophenoxy)acetate (**6b**) (Scheme 1). The IR spectra showed a character-

Scheme 1

ristic peaks at 3364 cm^{-1} (-OH) and 1724 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$). Its NMR spectra depicts a characteristics triplet at δ 1.3 for six protons [-N(CH₂CH₃)₂] and a multiplet at δ 2.4–2.7 for six protons [-CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂] (Table 1).

(**9b**) and 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oate (**10b**), respectively, as evidenced from the TLC (2 spots). The mixture was then refluxed with diethylamine in the presence of absolute alcohol to get hydroxyl tertiary amines, (3-*N,N*-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(2-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oate (**11a**)

Table 1. NMR data of tertiary amines (**6a**, **6b**, **11a**, **11b**)

Tertiary amine	¹ H NMR (δ , ppm)	¹³ C NMR (δ , ppm)
	δ 1.33 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.38–2.60 (6H, m, -CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 3.60 (1H, s, -OH-), 3.95 (1H, m, -CH(OH)), 4.1–4.3 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -COOCH ₂), 4.9 (2H, s, -ArOCH ₂ -), 7.2–7.4.5 (4H, m, -Ar-H)	C1 = 168.4, C2 = 65.3, C4 = 155.7, C5 = 118.5, C6 = 129.7, C7 = 125.8, C8 = 129.3, C9 = 116.5, C11 = 67.5, C12 = 65.1, C13 = 59.3, C15, C17 = 49.7, C16, C18 = 12.7
	δ 1.35 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.4–2.6 (6H, m, -CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 3.58 (1H, s, -OH-), 3.90 (1H, m, -CH(OH)), 4.0–4.36 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -COOCH ₂), 4.96 (2H, s, -ArOCH ₂ -), 7.1–7.32 (4H, m, -Ar-H)	C1 = 168.2, C2 = 64.3, C4 = 153.9, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.7, C7 = 121.8, C8 = 127.5, C9 = 111.7, C11 = 68.5, C12 = 65.4, C13 = 59.7, C15, C17 = 50.0, C16, C18 = 12.9
	δ 1.24 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.40–2.63 (6H, m, -CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 3.57 (1H, s, -OH-), 3.8–3.9 (1H, m, -CHOH), 4.2–4.4 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -COOCH ₂), 6.4 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 1.5 Hz, =CHCOO-), 7.76–8.21 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.38 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15 Hz, Ph-CH=)	C1 = 165.6, C2 = 115.7, C3 = 145.7, C4 = 126.5, C5 = 148.5, C6 = 124.3, C7 = 127.9, C8 = 135.7, C9 = 126.9, C11 = 68.5, C12 = 65.7, C13 = 58.7, C15, C17 = 49.7, C16, C18 = 12.7
	δ 1.26 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.4–2.6 (6H, m, -CH ₂ N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 3.68 (1H, s, -OH-), 3.8–3.9 (1H, m, -CHOH), 4.2–4.4 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -COOCH ₂), 6.4 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15 Hz, =CHCOO-), 7.18 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 15 Hz, Ph-CH=), 7.54–7.67 (4H, m, Ar-H)	C1 = 165.8, C2 = 115.2, C3 = 145.1, C4 = 133.8, C5, C9 = 130.5, C6, C8 = 127.5, C7 = 134.9, C11 = 68.8, C12 = 65.4, C13 = 58.9, C15, C17 = 50.6, C16, C18 = 13.1

Tertiary amines with cinnamic acid moieties were prepared by reacting 2-nitrocinnamic acid (**8a**, prepared from 2-nitrobenzaldehyde (**7a**)) and 4-Cl cinnamic acid (**8b**, prepared from 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (**7b**) by Knoevenagel reaction) separately with excess of epichlorohydrin in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ to get the mixture of oxiran-yl-methyl-3-(2-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oate (**9a**) and 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyl-3-(2-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oate (**10a**); oxiran-yl-methyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oate

and (3-*N,N*-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-enoate (**11b**), respectively. The cinnamic acid moieties procured for the above preparation were assigned *E* geometry by the comparison with the m.p.s of the acids reported in the literature and by the doublets at δ 6.4 and 8.0, having coupling constant equal to 15 Hz, from the NMR spectra of tertiary amines prepared from these acids. The tertiary amines were characterized by the presence of characteristic bonds at 3368

cm^{-1} (-OH) and 1714 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) in its IR spectra and a triplet at δ 1.26 for six protons and multiplet at δ 2.4–2.6 for six protons in its NMR spectra (Table 1).

2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid was converted into corresponding ammonium salts by refluxing the acid with equimolar ratio of ethanolamine, diethylamine and piperidine separately in acetone. The acid was also quaternized following the same procedure with different tertiary amines; viz 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (**6a**), 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(2-chlorophenoxy)acetate (**6b**), (3-*N,N*-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(2-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oate (**11a**) and (3-*N,N*-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-enoate (**11b**).

Biological activity :

The newly synthesized salts of ammonia (**1a-g**) were tested for their efficacy as plant growth retardants on various parameters of growth on rice seeds (*Oryza sativa*). The effect of synthesized compounds on per cent seed germination, seedling growth (length of longest root, coleoptile and leaf), seedling dry mass and vigour index is shown in Tables 3–5. 2,4-D (a common systemic herbicide used in the control of broadleaf weeds) was used as an additional standard along with cycocel and ABA.

Table 3 shows the effect of ammonium salts on germination of rice after 48 h. Compared to control (water), germination of seeds in response to different concentrations of all the tested compounds was reduced by about 20 to 60 per cent in newly synthesized ammonium salts. The inhibitory effect enhanced with increase in concen-

Scheme 2

Table 2. NMR data of ammonium salts of 2,4-D (12a-g)

Compd	¹ H NMR (δ, ppm)	¹³ C NMR (δ, ppm)
<p>12a</p>	<p>δ 3.45 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -N⁺H₃CH₂), 3.60 (1H, s, -CH₂OH), 4.35 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH₂OH), 4.95 (2H, s, -OCH₂COO), 7.06 (3H, s, -N⁺H₃), 7.24-7.60 (3H, m, Ar-H)</p>	<p>C1 = 178.5, C2 = 78.4, C4 = 149.2, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.8, C7 = 129.8, C8 = 131.2, C9 = 116.5, C11 = 45.7, C12 = 74.3</p>
<p>12b</p>	<p>δ 1.65 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, -2CH₂CH₃), 3.38 (4H, m, -2CH₂CH₃), 4.98 (2H, s, -CH₂COO), 7.10 (2H, s, -N⁺H₂), 7.24-7.60 (3H, m, Ar-H)</p>	<p>C1 = 178.5, C2 = 78.4, C4 = 149.2, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.8, C7 = 129.8, C8 = 131.2, C9 = 116.5, C11, C13 = 42.8, C12, C14 = 11.5</p>
<p>12c</p>	<p>δ 1.69 (2H, m, -CH₂), 2.0 (4H, m, -2CH₂), 3.45 (4H, m, -2N⁺H₂(CH₂)), 5.0 (2H, s, -CH₂COO), 7.05 (2H, s, -N⁺H₂), 7.24-7.60 (3H, m, Ar-H)</p>	<p>C1 = 178.5, C2 = 78.4, C4 = 149.2, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.8, C7 = 129.8, C8 = 131.2, C9 = 116.5, C11, C15 = 48.5, C12, C14 = 25.7, C13 = 20.8</p>
<p>12d</p>	<p>δ 1.62 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.36-3.58 (6H, m, -CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.60 (1H, s, -OH-), 4.24 (1H, m, -CH(OH)), 4.40-4.58 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -COOCH₂), 4.9 (2H, s, -ArOCH₂-), 5.1 (2H, s, -CH₂COO) 7.05 (1H, s, -N⁺H), 7.24-7.60 (7H, m, -2Ar-H)</p>	<p>C1 = 178.5, C2 = 78.4, C4 = 149.2, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.8, C7 = 129.8, C8 = 131.2, C9 = 116.5, C11 = 58.6, C12 = 69.5, C13 = 72.4, C15 = 170.5, C16 = 62.5, C18 = 155.2, C19, C23 = 118.9, C20, C22 = 132.5, C21 = 125.6, C24, C26 = 47.2, C25, C27 = 9.8</p>
<p>12e</p>	<p>δ 1.62 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.36-3.50 (6H, m, -CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.58 (1H, s, -OH-), 4.24 (1H, m, -CH(OH)), 4.40-4.58 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, -COOCH₂), 4.9 (2H, s, -ArOCH₂-), 5.1 (2H, s, -CH₂COO), 7.03 (1H, s, -N⁺H), 7.24-7.60 (7H, m, -2Ar-H)</p>	<p>C1 = 178.5, C2 = 78.4, C4 = 149.2, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.8, C7 = 129.8, C8 = 131.2, C9 = 116.5, C11 = 58.6, C12 = 69.5, C13 = 72.4, C15 = 170.5, C16 = 61.5, C18 = 153.8, C19 = 121.7, C20 = 133.5, C21 = 120.4, C22 = 129.8, C23 = 119.5, C24, C26 = 47.2, C25, C27 = 9.8</p>

Table-2 (contd.)

12f

δ 1.62 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $-N(CH_2CH_3)_3$), 3.36–3.50 (6H, m, $-CH_2N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 3.57 (1H, s, $-OH-$), 4.24 (1H, m, $-CHOH$), 4.4–4.584 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $-COOCH_2$), 5.1 (2H, s, CH_2COO), 6.4 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, $=CHCOO-$), 7.03 (1H, s, $-N^+H$), 7.24–8.20 (7H, m, 2Ar-H), 8.38 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, $Ph-CH=$)

C1 = 178.5, C2 = 78.4, C4 = 149.2, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.8, C7 = 129.8, C8 = 131.2, C9 = 116.5, C11 = 58.6, C12 = 69.5, C13 = 72.4, C15 = 156.5, C16 = 115.6, C17 = 145.9, C18 = 125.7, C19 = 149.8, C20 = 125.6, C21 = 130.5, C22 = 136.7, C23 = 128.5, C24, C26 = 47.2, C25, C27 = 9.8

12g

δ 1.62 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $-N(CH_2CH_3)_3$), 3.36–3.50 (6H, m, $-CH_2N(CH_2CH_3)_2$), 3.57 (1H, s, $-OH-$), 4.24 (1H, m, $-CHOH$), 4.4–4.584 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $-COOCH_2$), 5.1 (2H, s, $-CH_2COO$), 6.4 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, $=CHCOO-$), 7.03 (1H, s, $-N^+H$), 7.18 (1H, d, J 15 Hz, $Ph-CH=$), 7.24–7.70 (7H, m, 2Ar-H)

C1 = 178.5, C2 = 78.4, C4 = 149.2, C5 = 123.7, C6 = 133.8, C7 = 129.8, C8 = 131.2, C9 = 116.5, C11 = 58.6, C12 = 69.5, C13 = 72.4, C15 = 156.5, C16 = 115.6, C17 = 145.9, C18 = 135.9, C19, C23 = 130.5, C20, C22 = 127.5, C21 = 132.3, C24, C26 = 47.2, C25, C27 = 9.8

Table 3. Effect of ammonium salts of 2,4-D on seed germination (%) and length of longest root in cm) of *Oryza sativa* (PR-114)

Compd.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)								CD (5%)
	0	5	25	50	100	300	400	500	
H ₂ O	98 (6.83)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1a	-	68 (0.14)	65 (-)	51 (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	1.14 (0.12)
1b	-	63 (0.12)	60 (-)	47 (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	1.12 (0.15)
1c	-	59 (0.10)	56 (-)	40 (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	1.17 (0.10)
1d	-	63 (0.11)	60 (-)	56 (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	1.20 (0.14)
1e	-	65 (0.10)	60 (-)	53 (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	1.13 (0.13)
1f	-	60 (0.13)	58 (-)	50 (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	1.23 (0.17)
1g	-	67 (0.08)	53 (-)	50 (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	1.32 (0.16)
CCC	-	80 (4.12)	80 (3.96)	77 (3.83)	73 (2.70)	71 (2.10)	70 (1.52)	70 (0.76)	0.98 (0.16)
2,4-D	-	80 (0.76)	75 (0.34)	75 (-)	72 (-)	65 (-)	63 (-)	62 (-)	0.94 (0.18)
ABA	-	60 (0.09)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

trations of tested compounds. No seed germination was observed in the medium supplemented with 100–500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration of synthesized ammonium salts. In the seedling growth experiment, the growth of root was completely inhibited above the concentration of 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of all tested compounds (Table 3). The root length of seedlings treated with different concentrations of tested compounds showed more reduction as compared to that of 2,4-D at 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ which ranged between 81–89 per cent. Further, the inhibitory effect of synthesized salts was more marked when compared with CCC treatments. The length of coleoptile was reduced by 96–94% in various concentration of quaternary ammonium compounds (1d-g) show 96–94% reduction in length of coleoptile as compared with 2,4-D (Table 4). The elongation growth of first leaf was also affected by treatment with synthesized ammonium salts. The leaf length is highly reduced by the treatment with synthesized ammonium salts which ranged between 76–80% as compared with 2,4-D and 88–90% compared with CCC at 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (Table 4). Further increase in the concentrations of ammonium salts,

completely stopped leaf growth.

The effect of newly synthesized ammonium compounds of phenoxyacetic acid moiety on dry mass and vigour index of rice seedlings is shown in Table 5. The reduction in dry mass is found to be 90–94 per cent at 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration over control (water). It is evident from the data that the vigour index of rice seedlings decreased with increase in concentration of the synthesized compounds. The vigour index is found to decrease by 81–90 per cent in the newly synthesized ammonium salts at 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ when compared with 2,4-D.

The plant growth retardant activity of ammonium salts is reported to be more than that of 2,4-D (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid) herbicide itself. This shows that the conversion of acid into ammonium salts modifies its physical and biological characteristics; facilitating its use and increasing its effectiveness as the ammonium salts are solid in nature and increases the solubility of the compound in water, thus facilitating its handling and application as herbicide or plant growth retardant.

Table 4. Effect of ammonium salts of 2,4-D on coleoptile length (cm) and (leaf length in cm) of *Oryza sativa* (PR-114)

Compd.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)								CD (5%)
	0	5	25	50	100	300	400	500	
H ₂ O	1.90 (7.23)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1a	-	0.20 (0.56)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.12 (0.19)
1b	-	0.18 (0.50)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.11 (0.21)
1c	-	0.15 (0.47)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.13 (0.23)
1d	-	0.06 (0.52)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.15 (0.21)
1e	-	0.05 (0.48)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.19 (0.17)
1f	-	0.07 (0.51)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.17 (0.19)
1g	-	0.04 (0.47)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.18 (0.14)
CCC	-	1.30 (4.73)	1.20 (4.33)	0.93 (3.56)	0.89 (2.93)	0.80 (1.90)	0.73 (1.90)	0.73 (1.60)	0.14 (0.25)
2,4-D	-	1.26 (2.36)	0.87 (1.12)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	0.10 (0.21)
ABA	-	0.05 (0.50)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 5. Effect of ammonium salts of 2,4-D on dry mass (g) and (vigour index in g) of *Oryza sativa* (PR-114)

Compd.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)							
	0	5	25	50	100	300	400	500
H ₂ O	0.085	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	(8.33)							
1a	-	0.008	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.54)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
1b	-	0.007	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.44)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
1c	-	0.005	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.29)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
1d	-	0.007	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.44)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
1e	-	0.006	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.39)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
1f	-	0.008	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.48)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
1g	-	0.006	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.40)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
CCC	-	0.080	0.073	0.059	0.048	0.037	0.035	0.028
		(6.40)	(5.84)	(4.54)	(3.50)	(2.62)	(2.45)	(1.96)
2,4-D	-	0.037	0.019					
		(2.96)	(1.43)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
ABA	-	0.005	-	-	-	-	-	-
		(0.30)						

Experimental

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was employed for testing the purity of analytical samples. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker Avance II NMR spectrometer at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ , ppm). IR spectra were recorded as neat liquid on Perkin-Elmer-800 spectrometer. All organic compounds were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄.

2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (1) :

2,4-Dichlorophenol (8.1 g, 0.05 mol) and chloroacetic acid (4.75 g, 0.05 mol) were melted together on water bath and NaOH (4 g in 16.5 ml of H₂O, 6 N) was added to it drop wise with stirring and then mixture was heated to 60–70 °C for 3 h with occasional shaking. It was diluted with water and acidified with conc. HCl and precipitates thus formed were filtered, washed and dried to get 2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (1), m.p. 133–135 °C (lit. m.p. 134–138 °C), yield 8.6 g (85%).

3-(Diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (6a) and 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(2-chlorophenoxy)acetate (6b) :

4-Chlorophenol (2a)/2-chlorophenol (2b) separately (6.43 g, 0.05 mol) and chloroacetic acid (4.75 g, 0.05 mol) were melted together on water bath and NaOH (4 g in 16.5 ml of H₂O, 6 N) was added to it drop wise with stirring and then mixture was heated to 60–70 °C for 3 h with occasional shaking. After diluting with water and acidified with conc. HCl, the precipitates thus formed were filtered, washed and dried to get *p*-chlorophenoxy acetic acid (3a, 4-CPA), m.p. 155–156 °C (lit. m.p. 157–159 °C), yield 8.3 g (88%) or *o*-chlorophenoxy acetic acid (3b, 2-CPA), m.p. 132–135 °C, yield 6.53 g (70%).

The mixture of 4-CPA/2-CPA separately (6.5 g, 0.03 mol), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (11.2 g, 0.08 mol) and epichlorohydrin (120 ml) was refluxed under stirring for 13 h. The reaction mixture was filtered, filtrate was concentrated and residue was extracted with benzene. The organic phase was washed with 10% NaOH, water, saturated aqueous NaCl, dried and concentrated to afford the mixture of (4a/4b) and (5a/5b) which was checked by TLC. The above mixture (4.5 g) and diethylamine (9.6 ml) were refluxed in absolute alcohol for 1 h. Most of alcohol was distilled off and residue was diluted with water. It was extracted with ether followed by washing with water. Removal of solvent from the dried extract (over anhyd. Na₂SO₄), followed by the distillation under reduced pressure afforded the hydroxy tertiary amines : 3-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxypropyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-acetate (6a), b.p. 108–110°/7–8 mm of Hg, yield 2.6 g (45%); ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3364, 2940, 2927, 2860, 1724, 1637, 1414, 1228, 1190, 1124, 1046, 830, 756, 695/ (6b), b.p. 106–108°/3–4 mm of Hg, yield 3.9 g (58%); ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3392, 2973, 2940, 2815, 1725, 1636, 1459, 1202, 1063, 977, 863, 789.

(3-N,N-Diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(2-nitrophenyl)prop-2-enoate (11a) and (3-N,N-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-enoate (11b) :

A mixture of 2-nitrobenzaldehyde (7a, 4.5 g, 0.03 mol)/4-chlorobenzaldehyde (7b, 4.2 g, 0.03 mol), malonic acid (6.2 g, 0.06 mol), pyridine (8 ml) and piperidine (2–3 drops) as a catalyst were refluxed for 3 h. The mixture was cooled and poured into excess of water con-

taining enough of HCl (20 ml of HCl + 80 ml of H₂O) to react with pyridine. The precipitates thus formed were filtered, washed and dried to give unsaturated acid, 3-(2-nitrophenyl)-prop-2-en-1-oic acid (**8a**), yield 3.2 g (71%), m.p. 242–245 °C (lit. m.p. 244–246 °C, *E* isomer)/3-(4-chlorophenyl)-prop-2-en-1-oic acid (**8b**), yield 5.3 g (96%), m.p. 247–249 °C (lit. m.p. 249–251 °C, *E* isomer) 3-(2-Nitrophenyl)-prop-2-en-1-oic acid (**8a**, 4.8 g, 0.024 mol)/3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-oic acid (**8b**, 4.6 g, 0.025 mol), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (10.4 g, 0.075 mol) and epichlorohydrin (120 ml) were refluxed under stirring for 13 h. The reaction mixture was filtered, filtrate was concentrated and residue was extracted with benzene. The organic phase was washed with 10% NaOH, water, saturated aqueous NaCl, dried and concentrated to afford the mixture of (**9a/9b**) and (**10a/10b**) which was checked by TLC (2 spots).

The above mixture and diethylamine were refluxed in absolute alcohol for 1 h. Most of alcohol was distilled off and residue was diluted with water. It was extracted with ether followed by washing with water. Removal of ether from the dried extract (over anhyd. Na₂SO₄), followed by the distillation under reduced pressure afforded the hydroxy tertiary amine (**11a**), b.p. 110–112°/3–4 mm of Hg, yield 2.2 g (41%), v_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3365, 2975, 2938, 2870, 1717, 1642, 1569, 1528, 1453, 1385, 1350, 1294, 1205, 1085, 1047, 923, 885, 801, 758, 735/(**11b**), b.p. 110–120°/10–12 mm of Hg, yield 2.8 g (57%), v_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3368, 2974, 2945, 2870, 1714, 1642, 1593, 1492, 1460, 1407, 1370, 1313, 1272, 1205, 1175, 1090, 1044, 1014, 985, 912, 824, 735.

Preparation of salts of ammonia

General procedure for the preparation of ammonium salts (12a-g)

All the syntheses were carried out under reflux using a molar ratio acid : amine (ethanolamine, diethylamine, piperidine and all synthesized amine) and acetone as reaction medium. The amine was added drop-wise to the stirred solution of the acid in acetone. After the addition was over, the mixture was refluxed under stirring for 30 min. The removal of solvent (acetone) afforded a thick material. Scratching of the thick residue with dry ether (to remove if any unreacted tertiary amine and acid) followed by decantation of the solvent afforded a thick non-

crystalline salt of ammonia (yields 85–95%). Spectral data are given in Table 2.

Biological activity

The germination studies were carried out by using uniform size seeds of *Oryza sativa* (PR-114) in three replicas which were surface sterilized by 0.1 per cent mercuric chloride solution and were thoroughly washed before keeping for germination. The petridishes (9 cm diameter) lined with double layer of filter paper were used. The sterilized seeds were placed on filter paper of petridish and moistened by adding 10 ml of various test solutions of different concentrations (5, 25, 50, 100, 300, 400 and 500 ppm). Each petridish was kept at 28 ± 2° for 7 days in BOD incubator for germination studies.

Following observations were recorded:

Seed germination [expressed in percent seed germination after 48 h]

Seedling growth

The data on length of root, shoot (coleoptile), and leaf were measured after 7 days of germination using centimetre scale. For getting dry mass, samples were dried at 70 °C for 72 h in an oven and weighed.

Vigour index

VI = percent germination, X = total seedling dry mass

For controls, seeds were germinated in distilled water. CCC, ABA and 2,4-D were used as standards for calibrating the potential of tested compounds as retardant or inhibitor.

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References

- 1 B E Whippker and I McCall *Hort Technology* 2000 10 209
- 2 M Grozav and M Crisan, *EJEAF Che*, 2004 3 710
- 3 T J Banko and M A Stefani *J Environ Hort*, 1995 13 22
- 4 A Pobudkiewicz, *Folia Hort*, 2000b 12, 99
- 5 N A Richard, 'Plant Growth Substances Principles and

- Applications", Chapman & Hall, New York, 277
- 6 M L Sharma and H K Jagdeo, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 2004, **81**, 883
- 7 M L Sharma and M Bala, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 2005, **82**, 975
- 8 R Khanna, A K Saksena, V K Srivastava and K Shankar, *Indian J Chem , Sect B*, 1990, **29**, 1056
- 9 P Ashthana, M Prasad and S N Rastogi, *Indian J Chem , Sect B*, 1987, **26**, 330
- 10 J Zaagsma and T W Nauta, *J Med Chem* , 1977 **20**, 527
- 11 S D Samat, S M Gupta and R A Kulkarni, *Indian J Chem , Sect B*, 1980, **19**, 524
- 12 S El-Meligie, A K El-Ansary, M M Said and M M M Hussein, *Indian J Chem , Sect B*, 2001, **40** 62
- 13 H Obase, Y Yamada and S Kudo, *J Med Chem* , 1977, **20**, 394